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The beginning of a novel from page to screen: the example of *Pride and Prejudice* (1813 and 1940)

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Abstract

Nowadays, the relationship between literature and film is so important that it is impossible to ignore how many of the great classics have been adapted for the cinema. English literature and Jane Austen are certainly no exception and *Pride and Prejudice* is a classic that boasts a number of adaptations for film and TV. Of particular interest for this paper is Robert Z. Leonard's 1940 adaptation, famous, among other things, for being the first film adaptation of an Austen novel. The interest of this paper is to see how Chapter 1 and especially the opening sentence of the novel were adapted in Leonard's film, and to demonstrate how images can help in the interpretation of Jane Austen's written words.

Keywords: Jane Austen, *Pride and Prejudice*, Robert Z. Leonard, *Pride and Prejudice* 1940 film, Literature and Cinema, Incipit from novel to film, *Pride and Prejudice*: the incipit.

Introduction: Jane Austen and the cinema

One has only to look at the films that have been released in cinemas recently to see that literature plays a decisive role in the choices of producers and directors. Literary production, especially in English, lies at the heart of successful films,

providing stories that are widely read and appreciated by an international audience. John Grisham's legal thrillers are a case in point: his novels have a wide readership and their cinema adaptations have brought in substantial box office receipts.

When it comes to the classics, however, the process acquires broader cultural overtones and, perhaps, a more select audience in terms of literary skills and knowledge. William Shakespeare and Jane Austen provide two perfect examples, their works being still read, studied and adapted, perhaps more nowadays than ever before. As Lisa Hopkins explains, these adaptations "benefit from the very considerable cultural capital of their respective authors"¹ and nowadays it is almost impossible to find anyone who has not heard of them. They both wrote memorable works and enriched our language with expressions that have become commonplace over time. For example, Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* is a well-known novel and its opening sentence is undoubtedly one of the most remembered and quoted, both in literature and in the media, where it has put many a film director to the test.

The aim of this essay is to examine the significance of this opening sequence and to see how it was adapted in 1940, when the first film adaptation of the novel was released. As this essay will demonstrate, Austen's opening sentence in *Pride and Prejudice* encapsulates the culture of an era which still holds great appeal for cinema audiences. The reasons for this interest are to be found in the style adopted by the author and the themes addressed in her novels, as was already pointed out by some 19th century critics at the time. Thomas Babington Macaulay defined her the "prose Shakespeare", while Sir Walter Scott admired her "talent for describing the involvement and

1. Hopkins 2012: 241.

feelings and characters of ordinary life”, and George Henry Lewes stated that she was “the greatest artist who has ever written, using the term to signify the most perfect mastery over the means to her end”.² The greatness that 19th-century critics attributed to Jane Austen has also been confirmed in the centuries since, when her works have never been out of print, but rather have proved evergreen stories suitable for readers of any age and cultural background. In the 20th century in particular, the fondness for this Regency author turned into an “Austenmania which [...] produced a virtual industry flourishing widely in the United States and England”.³ Films and television series have provided audiences with adaptations and transpositions in time and place; merchandise like dolls and bags have encouraged her fame to spread among ordinary readers; the conservation of monuments and properties by the National Trust has increased the demand for literary tourism in the areas associated with her life and her works – with the advent of the new millennium, Jane Austen has turned into “a phenomenon that has crystallized at a particular moment in our own contemporary culture”.⁴ The reasons for this resounding and continued success may be traced in a survey reported by the BBC, confirming that people love Jane Austen because “she is writing about people and their problems”, because she knows how to “constantly surprise readers” and, finally, simply because she is a genius.⁵ Despite her being distant in time and belonging to a different mentality, Jane Austen appeals to

2. Thompson 2003: 19. The quotations from Macauley, Scott and Lewes are all from this source.

3. Pucci & Thompson 2003: 1.

4. Ibid.

5. Halford 2017: <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-england-40644085>

21st-century readers in search of romance and cultural roots in the past – her name in fact blurs the lines between high culture and low culture, academic studies and pop studies. To put it in Ian Watt's words,

“she was able to combine into a harmonious unity the advantages both of realism of presentation and realism of assessment, of the internal and of the external approaches to character; her novels have authenticity without diffuseness or trickery, wisdom of social comment without a garrulous essayist, and a sense of the social order which is not achieved at the expense of the individuality and autonomy of the characters”⁶

The success of all her novels has found further confirmation in the cinema, where her stories have inspired masterpieces and allowed great actors and actresses to measure themselves against her characters. The cinema has proved to be an excellent instrument for celebrating this late 18th-century author and for showcasing the characteristics of her style and world. She has been appropriated by the screen primarily as an author of love stories,⁷ which are good stories that appeal particularly to a female audience. Besides this, we should also consider that these stories are now in the public domain and that their adaptations require neither expensive special effects nor exclusive locations.⁸ Jane Austen's novels provide directors with everything they need to create a successful film, and *Pride and Prejudice*, her masterpiece, and its long list of adaptations supply clear evidence of this. Published in 1813, *Pride and Prejudice* is just one of the many examples of 19th-century novels that were adapted for the screen, both large and small, during the 20th century: the fact

6. Watt 1957: 297.

7. Ivi: 242.

8. Parrill 2002: 3.

that it tells a good story, has prestigious cultural associations and is out of copyright (which makes it cost-effective), makes it popular with audiences in any country.⁹ Besides this, as Martine Voiret explains, “costume drama appeals to the public for a complex set of reasons. [...] they allow the spectator to step out of the constraints of his time to try out different selves of identities. [...] they give the spectator license to identify with roles or characteristics now devalued. [...] they bring us back to an era when men could still be the locus of the beautiful”.¹⁰ In other words, this novel makes us daydream and is our passport to a magical and idyllic world.

Set in Regency England, in a period of hardship for the country, ruled by a mad king supplanted by his lascivious son, and in the hands of a government incapable of dealing with the consequences of the First Industrial Revolution, the loss of the American colonies and the Napoleonic threat, which sought to settle the account, once and for all, of the French Revolution,¹¹ this novel of manners¹² focuses on the quiet and conventional life of

9. Troost 2007: 75.

10. Voiret 2003: 229-230.

11. For the historical context of Regency England, see Sales 1996 and Smith 2004.

12. In the last decades of the 18th century a new subgenre of novels evolved in relation to women writers and their focus on social detail. Starting from its meaning, in which morality and society intersect, the term ‘manner’ emphasises the strong moralistic component in the behaviour that Regency people had to adopt in society. These novels rely on, and in some cases, replace, the so-called ‘conduct books’, actual codes of conduct to be followed in the various circumstances of everyday life. The stories told were inspired by the novels of Frances Burney and were intended to teach young girls how to become honest and respectable women and good wives. (see: Meyer Spacks 2006: 160-190).

a family living in the southern English countryside – a family of the gentry, the Bennets lead a very simple and unsophisticated life at Longbourn, their estate not far from Meryton. The mother of five daughters, Mrs. Bennet is particularly active in the search for a husband for her daughters, who must manage between the embarrassing silliness of their mother and the affectionate indifference of their father. The social conventions around which the experiences of these characters revolve provide the background to a world that, although difficult for us to accept today, underpins the author's world. To understand this is to understand Austen's world and novels.

This is the reason why the cinema finds Austen's novels so inspiring and decides to re-present them in ever new and original adaptations. With cinema, the challenge is not to make the novels known through words, but also through images, helping the audience recreate the atmosphere of Regency England, its fashions, its countryside, its language register and all the other aspects related to ordinary life.

Of all the adaptations of *Pride and Prejudice*, here we have chosen to look at Robert Leonard's masterpiece of 1940 and see how the beginning of the film allows the audience to recognise Austen's famous incipit and takes them back in their imagination to the time when the novel was written.

Jane Austen's text

Let's now turn to the first chapter of the novel. As Austen's readers know, it is made up of three sequences, the first and third of which consist of information and clarifications by the narrator and frame the central part, which contains the conversation between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet.

The opening sentence is known world-wide and is also one of the most exploited in quotations and parodies.

It is a truth universally acknowledged, that a single man in possession of a good fortune, must be in want of a wife.¹³

The third-person voice of an omniscient narrator, external to the story, is what welcomes the readers as they open the cover of the book and meet the first page of the novel. Although it is so short, this incipit provides some fundamental information on the plot of the novel and indeed on the author's world. The grammatical subject beginning the whole sequence is a neutral third person singular pronoun, *It*, introducing us to what Austen says is a conviction known and shared by everyone in late 18th-century England. The conviction thus introduced is actually a truth, a word Austen must have chosen with considerable care and thought. The precision of this word invites readers to consider the alternatives Austen had at her disposal: rule, statement, certainty, reality, principle... the fact that Austen chose the word *truth* must thus be meaningful and must bring something important to the global sense of the sentence. As explained in the *Oxford English Dictionary*, *truth* means in fact: 'Something that conforms with fact or reality',¹⁴ in other words, and in Austen's mind, something everyone knows to be the case. For this reason, the "universally acknowledged" which follows refers to an idea which cannot be put up for discussion, nor denied or misunderstood. The "truth universally acknowledged" in Austen's text relies on a series of convictions and practices that sprang from a strict code of conventions that existed in Regency England, widely shared by

13. Austen 2016: 3.

14. *Oxford English Dictionary Online*, https://www.oed.com/dictionary/truth_n?tab=meaning_and_use#17399020

Austen's contemporaries - they knew that this truth was a rule defining and regulating people's behaviour in their particular world.

This established, Austen moves to explain what this truth consists of: "a single man in possession of a good fortune, must be in want of a wife." The idea is so well and clearly stated that no one could mistake its meaning: a wealthy single man is always in need of a wife. The precision of Austen's vocabulary helps the reader understand what she is talking about and what her novel will be about, each term contributing its own specific meaning to the expression of the general idea - if it is true that any unmarried man needs a wife to complete him and help him in his path through life, all the more reason to argue that a lonely, rich young man needs a wife to help him assert himself in society.

Wealth was in fact what kept Austen's world going, much more than the romances she described in her novels and her readers mostly appreciated. Money was however also one of the main concerns in the years when Austen was writing her masterpiece. The closing years of the 18th century had proved very difficult for England, both historically and economically. The winter of 1795 had been particularly harsh, putting a strain on the lives of the poorest, forcing parliament to sign a Poor Relief Act to alleviate the suffering of people in need. Economic difficulties were the topic of the day and Austen's knowledge of Adam Smith's theory made her more attentive to economic concerns and more sensitive to the living conditions of her contemporaries.¹⁵ Besides this, however, conventions attributed a crucial role to money

15. There is reason to believe that Jane Austen was familiar with Adam Smith's *Wealth of Nations*, published in 1776, and was more inclined towards a Tory view than the Whig view of Thomas Malthus, Edmund Burke and Frederic Eden.

in the marriage market, to the point that a good match was determined by the annual income of the suitor. The possession of a good fortune was what made the difference in Austen's world and what made a young man a good catch for any woman on the marriage market.

This idea is clearly stated in the second and final part of the introductory sentence quoted above: "must be in want of a wife". Austen manages to encapsulate the entire meaning of what she has written so far into a single item, a modal verb which gathers all the cultural, social and economic implications we have so far considered. *Must*, which is normally used to express obligation and deduction, here actually helps readers to deduce the logical consequence of what has just been stated and gives more strength and emphasis to what follows: "in want of a wife". The truthfulness of the concept just expressed is essentially based only on the precision with which the figure of the potential groom is sketched but is silent on any criteria concerning the potential bride. This lack of information entitles the reader to assume that any girl may be the one chosen for a husband: what really matters is the opportunity, not to say the advantage, that such a groom represents for any girl. This lack of information can only infer that this truth is described here by a woman and relies on a totally female consideration of the marriage market. Any woman would be perfect for a wealthy young man!

This assumption is confirmed by what follows:

However little known the feelings or views of such a man may be on his first entering a neighbourhood, this truth is so well fixed in the minds of the surrounding families that he is considered as the rightful property of some one or other of their daughters. (p. 3)

Short as it is, this passage is meant to bridge theory and practice and provide a further step in Austen's narration, allowing the readers to enter the world of her story and to meet its characters. Reading it, we discover that the statement in the opening sentence is here cast within a specific reality, that of a context familiar to the author, who thus introduces us to the world that forms the background to her story. The setting will be a neighbourhood, not a big city, but a small town typical of the English countryside. This is the place into which the young man previously introduced steps for the first time to find himself surrounded and observed by the families living there: he is in their hands and, having no say in the matter, will have to rely on their decisions.

What emerges from the paragraph above is in fact that those families are so aware of the truth so well expressed before, that they do not hesitate to put it into practice and turn it to their advantage – this young man is “the rightful property” of one of their daughters, the word *property* clearly hinting at that peculiar idea of marriage as an economic affair, a real business with a crucial social relevance. The harsh law of the marriage market prevented any importance being attached to the feelings and physical appearance of the young man who, by the mere fact of being wealthy, had to also be respectable, charming and in love.

In a handful of sentences, Austen has given the reader an insight into the culture behind her novel, and through the irony that shines through between the words, she invites them to see for themselves how well-fixed in the mind of her contemporaries that truth is. What follows, and what has been missing so far, is an example of the concrete application of this well-known truth introduced above.

The theoretical premises now complete, and the readers being fully introduced to the mental framework of Austen's world, the next sequence of the chapter is introduced with the task of bringing a typical example to the reader's attention.

'My dear Mr. Bennet,' said his lady to him one day, 'have you heard that Netherfield Park is let at last?' Mr. Bennet replied that he had not. 'But it is,' returned she; 'for Mrs. Long has just been here, and she told me all about it.' Mr. Bennet made no answer. 'Do not you want to know who has taken it?' cried his wife impatiently. (p. 3)

The reader is thus introduced to a conversation taking place between a husband and wife, with the former patiently listening to what the latter has to tell him: they occupy a position among 'one of the neighbouring families' mentioned in the first sequence. The scene, which takes place without a specific setting, can take place anywhere, thus leaving the reader free to choose the place they feel is most suitable. The reader does not know anything about this family, but can glean information about its life from the dialogue in this portion of the chapter: they must live in the countryside, somewhere in the south of England, as it can be inferred from the text; they are a couple like many others at that time; they have some daughters who are introduced through their words about them, each one with a special feature to recommend her – Jane is the prettiest, Lydia the most good-humoured and Lizzy her father's favourite: she "has something more of quickness than her sisters who are all silly and ignorant", he says.

The conversation revolves around a piece of news that Mrs. Bennet has learnt from Mrs. Long, an anonymous soul whose only role in this conversation is to demonstrate the existence of the neighbourhood, inhabited by families like the Bennets,

whose life is based on the social conventions in vogue at the time. Thus, what Mrs. Bennet reports to her husband must be the piece of news which, of all those shared during her friend's visit, has caught her attention and given her reassuring comfort about the possibility of finding a husband for her daughters – to her, the announcement of Netherfield Park being rented is important to the extent that the news anticipates the arrival of a wealthy young man in their neighbourhood. Mrs. Long informed her well and told her the kind of information she needed to start making wedding plans: his name is Bingley, he is from the north of England and has a very large fortune to rely on - “four or five thousand a year” is a large fortune indeed, confirmed by his arrival “in a chaise and four”, another item indicative of his wealth. This piece of news allows the reader to infer the Bennets' economic situation: if Mrs. Bennet feels enthusiastic about Mr. Bingley's fortune to the point of considering him a good match for one of her daughters, it means that her family is less wealthy than his.

The tone with which Mr. Bennet interacts with his wife lets Jane Austen's irony shine through, making the readers a part of what she thought about the marriage market of her time. Yet, the fact that money kept their world going did not prevent people from getting married for love: economics and romance were in fact two different sides of the same coin, both crucial in *Pride and Prejudice* and in Austen's life.¹⁶

16. As reported in her biography, at some point in her life Jane Austen met Tom Lefroy, the son of a wealthy family seeking social affirmation. They hit it off immediately, but when marriage began to be discussed, his family objected to Jane's simple social conditions and opposed the marriage. Lefroy left for Ireland and Jane never considered marriage again. For information of Jane Austen's life, please see Tomalin 1997: 114-121.

Once the news has been delivered and has brought about turmoil in the Bennets' neighbourhood and family, Austen's readers encounter the practical consequences of such a piece of news and discover what social convention expected Mr. Bennet to do to address the matter:

you must visit him as soon as he comes. [...]
you must indeed go and see Mr. Bingley when he comes into the neighbourhood [...]
indeed you must go, for it will be impossible for us to visit him if you do not. (p. 4)

Since it was unseemly for a woman to introduce herself to a man without being first introduced by her father or husband, Mr. Bennet is expected to visit Mr. Bingley first. This is what convention established and what was indispensable if Mrs. Bennet was to see her plans become reality. Once again, the modal verb, *must*, gives strength to the main verb and emphasises the importance of such conventions in an ordered and well-structured community. Austen's contemporaries were familiar with this procedure and, if on one hand Mrs. Bennet's requests were not unusual, Mr. Bennet's mocking and provoking tone would have made them laugh, rather than complain or worry. The ironic and playful bickering between husband and wife finds fulfilment in the last sequence of this chapter, where the nature of the two characters is revealed and explained to the reader:

Mr. Bennet was so odd a mixture of quick parts, sarcastic humour, reserve, and caprice, that the experience of three-and-twenty years had been insufficient to make his wife understand his character. *Her* mind was less difficult to develop. She was a woman of mean understanding, little information, and uncertain temper. When she was discontented, she fancied herself nervous. The business of her life was to get her daughters married; its solace was visiting and news. (p. 5)

In these closing remarks, Austen adds some information about this twenty-three-year-long marriage, based on respect for social conventions rather than on love and affection. The portraits Jane Austen offers are not based on physical appearance, but on the character and personality of both husband and wife, the former being more complex than the latter. Mr. Bennet is in fact said to be “so odd a mixture of quick parts, sarcastic humour, reserve, and caprice” that he is distracted from the silly concerns of a wife whose simplicity of mind makes her “a woman of mean understanding, little information, and uncertain temper”. A woman of her time, Mrs. Bennet only cares about her daughters being married and about her nerves, which plague her in the most trying moments of her life.

From page to screen

Released in cinemas on July 26, 1940, Leonard’s film¹⁷ was the very first film adaptation of this novel¹⁸ and followed a stage adaptation, which was performed on Broadway in 1935.¹⁹ The success of this adaptation inspired and encouraged the film producers to adapt it for the big screen, too. Designed to entertain audiences by providing them with a bit of levity amidst the horrors of the Second World War, which was in progress at the time, the film came out only a few days after the beginning of the Battle of Britain on July 10th, and only two months after Prime Minister Winston Churchill’s most famous speech - *I have nothing to offer but blood, toil, tears and sweat*, broadcast on the radio in May of that year.²⁰

17. Leonard 1940. All the images related to this film included in these pages are from this edition.

18. Carroll & Wiltshire 2013: 165.

19. Belton 2012: 177.

20. The speech is available on the following website: <https://www.youtube>.

The rights of the play were sold to Metro-Goldwyn-Mayer²¹ and the script was written by Jane Murfin and Aldous Huxley, who, starting from the premise that “the very fact of transforming the book into a picture must necessarily alter its whole quality in a profound way”,²² did their best with Jane Austen. The leading roles were given to Laurence Olivier and Greer Garson,²³ whose Mr. Darcy and Elizabeth Bennet give life to this condensed black and white version of the novel²⁴ - the plot is in fact told through a compressed sequence of events with rapid scene changes, and quick and witty dialogue, reminding the audience of Oscar Wilde’s comedies.²⁵ The cinema release was accompanied by publicity in line with the director’s choices and, as Brownstein says, in perfect Hollywood style: “Bachelors Beware! Five Gorgeous Beauties are on a Madcap Manhunt!”²⁶

Since the aim of the producers and director was especially to entertain the people in the occupied countries, Leonard’s *Pride and Prejudice* is not set in wartime, the war against France not even being mentioned and Napoleon’s defeat at Waterloo being a pale memory locked up in a remote past.²⁷ Devoid of any reference to war and focused on the love story between the protagonists, the film has all the main characteristics of a screwball comedy:²⁸ “a quest to find love, work, and money,

com/watch?v=80_HXIH724

21. Belton 2012: 177.

22. Brownstein 2001: 13.

23. Cartmell 2010: 6.1

24. Gymnich 2015: 18.

25. Sørbo 2014: 80.

26. Brownstein 2001:14.

27. Sørbo 2014: 81.

28. Parrill 2002: 50 and Sørbo 2014: 81.

an impetus to redefine the foundations of conjugal unions [...]. Comedies of optimism and the myth of crossing class boundaries”²⁹

Having said this, we can now consider the beginning of Leonard’s film and see how he chose to adapt Austen’s novel to the screen. Since a film director’s approach is different from a writer’s, most of the differences between novel and film are due to the fact that while Austen relied on the power of words, Leonard must do the same with images and entrust to them everything that Austen’s words say and describe.³⁰ Considering the way *Pride and Prejudice* begins, Leonard had to contend with one of the best-known incipits in English-language literature, elegantly constructed with words that, while evoking a blurry scenario for the screen, on the contrary offer very clear cultural and conceptual images on the page: they are the outlook of the world of her novel, the mentality behind that world and the explanation of every circumstance described in the story. We need only look at all the adaptations of *Pride and Prejudice* to realise that this short but meaningful passage has been totally ignored by film makers: no one has been able to adapt it entirely to the screen, or, perhaps, no one has decided to measure themselves against that. How could Leonard handle it? He is no exception, but, since an introduction had to be provided, he chose to create one which was in line with the kind of film he had in mind and the type of story he had to tell.

Accompanied by music that is both lively and romantic, the film gradually introduces the audience to a fairytale landscape,

29. Halbout 2023: 2.

30. This is an important point which can be found fully developed in Fumagalli 2020 and Seger 1992.

sketched in white on a grey screen. After the opening credits, a sign captures the audience's attention, indicating the atmosphere of the story about to begin (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Opening credits © MGM 1940

If the background provides the audience with a drawing of a country landscape, consisting of an outdoor space with trees and flowers enclosing a path that leads the viewer into the distance, the foreground offers a handful of words introducing the audience to a world now lost in an idealized past. The story which is going to be told took place in Old England, which is to say in a distinct part of the British Isles, in a period in the distant past. This is enough to immerse the audience in a magical atmosphere of romance, suspended in time and place, far removed from contemporary industrialized England - a handful of words and almost Victorian costumes help to reconstruct the atmosphere of fairy tales whose initial *Once upon a time...* closely resembles the world evoked here. For the 1940 audience, this ideal land had turned into a threatened

paradise, where hatred had replaced love. The film thus starts with a longing, backward glance towards the old world, and an implicit reminder to cherish it”³¹

This time, however, the fairyland is not a small and faraway kingdom, but a typical English country village with which Austen’s readers would be familiar - they did not need indications or descriptions to imagine something they could find anywhere in the English countryside. The situation was quite different for the 1940 audience who, unlike their predecessors, could not know what Meryton would look like.

Figure 2 and Figure 3.
Opening credits and Meryton © MGM 1940

31. Sørbo 2014: 85.

Leonard had to describe it and so started with a beautiful drawing of Meryton (Figure 2), which gradually turns into a real, inhabited village on the screen (Figure 3): the hens in the street and the fruit seller plying his wares from a cart leave no doubt as to the coherent reconstruction of the village, making it real on the screen and accurate on a historical level. It is a sunny day and the white clouds in the sky do not seem to threaten the peaceful and relaxed atmosphere that reigns in Meryton. Here the harmonious relationship between man and nature has become reality, making Meryton an ideal place to live.

The scene opens on an ordinary day, with life going on as usual: people meet and talk amicably in the street, take a walk, go to church or go shopping, as they please. The audience's attention is drawn to a shop boy who, running in the street, leads the audience into a shop where they meet the first characters in the story. The shop is Meryton's haberdashery, an important meeting place for women in search of items to embellish their outfits (Figure 4). The characters we meet in the shop are two young women with their mother: they are Mrs. Bennet and her eldest daughters, Jane and Lizzy.

Figure 4. Meryton's haberdashery © MGM 1940

Figure 5. Meryton's haberdashery © MGM 1940

This choice to set the beginning of the film in a shop is not faithful to the novel, but is nevertheless logical and consistent with the world Leonard means to create. Moreover, Jane Austen does not provide her readers with a setting for the opening sequence and this fact authorises the director to imagine an alternative, but plausible, context that could shape the beginning of his film. A haberdashery shop was in fact not only a place for purchases, but also a meeting place where news circulated, gossip reigned supreme and women could talk about fashion and society (Figure 5). To help the viewer enter into that reality, Leonard takes them to a shop typically frequented by women and introduces them to the news of Mr. Bingley's arrival as an important piece of news, capable of disturbing the tranquillity of the village. The audience therefore witnesses this news and becomes, together with Mrs. Bennet and her daughters, the bearer of it to Mr. Bennet. Involvement in the plot is thus assured: the eye of the spectator coincides with that of the novel's narrator, but with a difference: to continue to hold their attention and maintain

their involvement, the story is only unfolded to the spectator step by step on the screen. Leonard thus displays to the audience how Mrs. Bennet was informed of Mr. Bingley's arrival by her sister, just minutes before his arrival in Meryton and his carriage stopping outside the shop. It is as if Leonard wanted words to be supported and confirmed by images, which is exactly what happens when adapting novels to films. The news related to Mr. Darcy's arrival in the same carriage is then anticipated by Lady Lucas and confirmed, in the same way as in Bingley's case, shortly later. This is another difference from the novel, where Austen makes no reference to Mr. Darcy and introduces him only some chapters later, at a public ball in Meryton. As a consequence of the adaptation process, Leonard decided to present all the main characters in the opening sequence of his film, so as to immediately introduce the protagonists of the romance to the audience. In this way, however, he changes the narrative pace and deprives the audience of the surprise of meeting Mr. Darcy, the true Prince Charming of the story, in due course.

Figure 6. Mr. Bingley and Mr. Darcy arrive at Meryton © MGM 1940

The two wealthy men appear in their carriage with some ladies who are Mr. Bingley's sisters. Silly as she is, Mrs. Bennet rushes out of the shop and, after gathering all her daughters, rushes back home to tell Mr. Bennet this great piece of news.

Given the emotion and apprehension with which she learns the news, Mrs. Bennet becomes the focus of the director's attention as he guides the audience to focus on her and become familiar with her nature, temperament and stupidity. Exaggerating her silliness, Leonard somewhat ridicules her and turns her into the comic character of this sequence of scenes. Her struggle against time and her daughters, who do not seem to share their poor mother's concern, reaches its climax when her daughter Mary is so engrossed in the purchase of a book that not only does she not notice anything, but seems to be unaffected by the big news. Far from sharing her sisters' flirtatiousness and prissiness, Mary prefers to devote herself to reading Burke's *Philosophical Enquiry* rather than buying frills for clothes in which she shows no interest.

Figure 7. The Bennets in Meryton © MGM 1940

Figure 8. The coach chase © MGM 1940

All her daughters summoned (Figure 7), Mrs. Bennet rushes home, engaging on the way in a race with Lady Lucas's coach which is rushing home with the same purpose (Figure 8). Her daughters do not seem to share their mother's anxiousness to arrive first: they look bewildered and amused at the same time, their looks indicating how well they know their mother and her inexhaustible rivalry with the neighbourhood ladies when it comes to securing a good husband for her daughters.

This extremely dynamic and comic coach race, totally invented by Leonard, comes to an end with the Bennets' arrival at home. There the audience finds a typical Regency country house, dignified, clean and orderly, surrounded by a garden, immersed in the quiet of a sunny day, with flourishing trees and colourful flowerbeds. It is the quiet introduction to Mr. Bennet in his peaceful and silent library, the room where he spends most of his time. He feels perfectly at ease there, away from the bickering of female voices, the laughter of still-teenage daughters, the exclamations of his wife, ... away from the world based on social conventions and comprised

of balls, parties and fashionable weddings. Mr. Bennet's library is an oasis of peace where he feels most comfortable and can isolate himself from his large and noisy family.

When Mrs. Bennet rushes into the room and inevitably interrupts Mr. Bennet's activity, the audience is with him, looking out of the window and smiling at the arrival of his family. In this way, Leonard allows the audience to change of perspective: now the viewer is no longer with the happy group, but with Mr. Bennet, waiting at home. Leonard introduces him sitting in an armchair reading a book: he is in fact the embodiment of wisdom and knowledge, he looks devoted to his family and used to his wife's troublesome nerves. Compared to his wife, who is voluminous in her colourful dresses and high hats, we find that he is a small man with a low reassuring voice, which constantly contrasts with the shrill sound of his wife's voice.

It is in this library that the conversation between husband and wife, told by Austen in the first chapter of the novel, eventually takes place and Mr. Bennet learns about the arrival of the two gentlemen in Meryton: this is where the novel begins. Unlike the reader, the viewer already knows the news and is thus only a witness to Mr. Bennet's reaction to his wife's words.

If we compare the conversation in the novel with the one in the film,³² we see that they are more or less the same length, which means that they take more or less the same amount of time to read and be performed. In Austen's novel, the conversation between Mr. and Mrs. Bennet is embedded in the heart of the chapter, being preceded and followed by some sentences by the narrator.³³

32. The script of the film is available at this website: http://www.script-orama.com/movie_scripts/p/pride-and-prejudice-script-austen.html

33. Toner 2020: 133.

As Anne Toner remarks, the dialogue, which is well structured,

consists of twenty-nine turns. There are only six attributions of speech and four of those attributions occur in quick succession at the opening of the dialogue, establishing the alternating pattern of only two speakers. Attribution then falls away and the reader depends on their emerging knowledge of the characters' opinions and the rhythm of the exchange to know who is speaking when.³⁴

In other words, Austen omits essential narrative superstructures, with 'he said' and 'she said' being absent from this conversation.³⁵ If these omissions are relevant to the understanding of the written text, they are certainly superfluous, and therefore not necessary, for the film version of the conversation – the image in fact compensates for the lack of indications in the original text. As can be inferred from the comparison between the the text and the script, Huxley and Murfin reshaped the conversation to make it consistent with the director's choices. Clearly, the references to what happened in the opening sequence, which is to say the details of the conversation at the shop and the coach race home, had to be introduced here to sound consistent with the story and establish a connection between before and after. However, many expressions from the original text were kept but then adapted to the new medium: the witty exchange between husband and wife perfectly suited the rules of rhythm and sound in this film which is a compressed version of the story:³⁶ the shortness of the characters' lines helps in fact with the speed and comedy of the scene, while the length of the original lines would have made the scene boring and slow.

34. *Ibid.*

35. *Ibid.*

36. Sørbo 2014: 83.

The two characters embody the personalities Austen gives them but differ from them in that the original characters are more detached from one another and live in a marriage of convenience, as many did at the time the novel was written: Mrs. Bennet is too silly to be taken seriously by her husband who seems to be totally unaffected by her anxiety to see her daughters married off. In this film, instead, Mr. and Mrs. Bennet seem to share a different kind of relationship: her silliness is simply something her husband has learnt to accept and endure, something to affectionately tease her about. What emerges from the Bennets' married life, and which will be the real message of this film, is that "love is independent from money: it is a matter of attraction and emotions only".³⁷ The consequence is that the Bennets' household in the film is a harmonious one, based on life-long understanding and affection (Figure 9). He is a mild man, always with a smile on his face and a benevolent patience when addressing his wife in a friendly tone. She is stupid and single-minded, blessed with a much better husband than in the novel.

Figure 9. Mr. and Mrs. Bennet © MGM 1940

37. Ivi: 85.

The idea behind the film is in fact to hail the traditional family as the only secure harbour in a period of ravaging war: Leonard puts here on screen a celebration of the Anglo-American family, the institution at the basis of a society which was collapsing under the pressure of war and was in many cases wracked by grief at the loss of loved ones. The aim was in fact to inspire confidence in the family and to invite people to continue to believe in its unifying and pacifist force. The Bennets thus prove to be a model of reference, a source of inspiration and a dream for all the young people looking for a better future.

Closing remarks

In *Janeites*, a story published in 1926, Rudyard Kipling hailed Austen as an English cultural icon and called her “fruitful in the highest sense”.³⁸ This idea is truer today than ever before as Austen’s ‘fruitfulness’ can be seen on a wide scale not only in literature, but also across media, from comics to cinema and TV series. In the case of *Pride and Prejudice*, one cannot forget the dozens of adaptations and parodies produced throughout the 20th and 21st centuries - one example above all, the BBC TV miniseries in 1995, left an indelible mark on our memory with Colin Firth as Mr. Darcy. Nor could one forget the lively and colourful Bollywood version, directed by Gurinder Chadha in 2004.

Austen’s masterpiece has also inspired a series of parodies where the protagonists are expected to deal with zombies, dog lovers, intricate love stories and teenage passions. The Web is full of films, long and short, recalling the story of Elizabeth and Darcy, sometimes struggling with problems at school,

38. Kipling 1994: 738.

sometimes focusing on their careers in the world of work. Such a wide range of products certainly satisfies a wide and varied public, at the risk, however, of disappointing a particularly demanding section of the public in the cultural and literary sphere.

In this rich and varied panorama of products related to *Pride and Prejudice*, the film we have considered here not only has the advantage of having been the initiator of the association between Austen and the cinema, but also has the merit of providing a love story that still enchants today. Although critical of Greer Garson as Elizabeth Bennet,³⁹ Laurence Olivier managed to bring a convincing Mr. Darcy to the screen with his all-English charm and his aristocratic bearing. The film exceeded Olivier's own expectations of success and received very positive reviews: the *New York Times* described it as "deliciously pert, the most crisp and crackling satire in costume that this corner can remember ever having seen on the screen", while the *Los Angeles Herald* appreciated the work of the actors involved.⁴⁰

From the literary point of view, Leonard's film is an interesting adaptation of Austen's novel as it provides evidence of how script and images go hand in hand in the long and delicate process of adapting a literary text. Due to the wartime period and

39. The story goes that Olivier, who was having a love affair with Vivien Leigh, wanted her in the role of Elizabeth Bennet. The studio had, however, other ideas: they preferred to avoid the risk of seeing the Olivier-Leigh love affair become public and have to deal with the consequent moral backlash. They thus chose Greer Garson, an English actress who was little more than a stranger to Olivier. See Turan 1989: <https://jasna.org/persuasions/printed/number11/turan.htm> (last visit: March 29, 2025).

40. *Ibid.* for both quotations.

the need to entertain an increasingly emotionally challenged audience, this film emphasizes the love story element whose appeal has been consecrated by time. It is a good compromise between love, family, concerns and ideals that reinforces the myth of the world created by Jane Austen.

The comparison of the opening sequence in the novel and in the film clearly shows the extent to which the film adaptation needed to make changes to the original text. The process from novel to film demanded the translation of Austen's text into a new medium. As Linda Seger explains, "Novels and films express themselves in different ways. Fiction uses words to tell a story, describe character, and build ideas. Films use image and action. They are essentially different mediums that resist each other as often as they cooperate".⁴¹ The same features can be recognised in the introductory sequences of both novel and film: both texts refer in fact to the same material that sets up the story, introduces the main characters and gives the information needed for the action to start.⁴² Moreover, they establish a problem in that the news of Mr Bingley's arrival triggers a series of actions that gradually cascade towards the happy ending.

If the words with which the novel begins betray the thoughts of the author and her era, the opening sequence of the film introduces the viewer to a small, perfect world, in which a community lives its ordinary simple life and hopefully welcomes the surprise of good news from outside. As Jane Austen herself once wrote to Anne Austen Lefroy, "Three or four families in a country village is the very thing to work on":⁴³ the microcosm formed by this community offered a

41. Seger 1992: 27.

42. Ivi: 1-27.

43. Austen 1925: 172.

particular form of society “focused around the institutions of country-house life”.⁴⁴ For a writer like Jane Austen, who grew up in the countryside of provincial England and disdained big cities, that world coincided with her world and represented THE world – all the rest was redundant to her eyes and mind. The community created in the film and through the opening sequence gives life to her world, to the point that the audience would not be surprised if they came across a young woman peeking out among the inhabitants of Meryton looking like Jane Austen herself. The world Leonard created for the film is in fact very similar to Regency country villages.

The reconstruction of the village of Meryton, besides being the location of the novel’s opening scene, or the description of the characters’ appearance, are clear examples of how Jane Austen’s style is suited to cinematic rendering. In particular, the lack of physical description of the characters allows the audience to create their own idea about the character: the resulting scenic freedom attributes the character’s personality and appearance to a specific actor or actress who may not embody what the audience had imagined while reading the novel. In other words, all this can be translated into actions that, put together, contribute to the success of the film and to the judgement the audience makes about it. The consequence is that the audience may question whether the actors are right for the part they are given: for example, is Laurence Olivier a good Mr. Darcy? How do the traits attributed to Austen’s character according to our imagination contribute to the realisation of Darcy’s character on screen? Although Olivier is an excellent Mr. Darcy, the audience is free to attribute a different look, different

44. Crang 2003:114.

mannerisms and a different interpretation to this character. The beauty of cinema lies precisely in transforming words into images, as Mc Kee says,⁴⁵ to make them real, or at least virtual, since they are on the screen. The 'show don't tell' formula is in fact the basis of any film adaptation that wants to reconstruct on screen the world described in the source novel.

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45. See McKee 1998.

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